

ACOUSTIC EMISSION SENSOR FOR IN-SITU MONITORING OF CARBON/CARBON PROCESSING

C. L. Yen and B. R. Tittmann

Department of Engineering Science and Mechanics
The Pennsylvania State University
University Park, PA 16802[USA]

ABSTRACT

A process sensor technique is described for monitoring First Carbonization of Carbon/Phenolic in the range from 25-750°C. The technique is based on the observation of acoustic emissions(AE) resulting from the onset and development of macroporosity. The AE data are obtained via an ultrasonic waveguide in contact with the part near its edge. The data show good run-to-run repeatability and point to a strong onset of microcracking near 500°C. An effect similar to that described by Kaiser is observed when the temperature is reduced and then raised again. The acoustic emissions stop and then start again but only after the same temperature is reached as before the decrease. When interpreted in terms of current understanding of the process, this result can be explained on the basis of tensile loading of the fiber network on the matrix during matrix shrinkage.

Keywords: acoustic emission, composites, Kaiser effect, carbon/carbon, in-situ process monitoring, macroporosity, carbon/phenolic.

I. INTRODUCTION

Current manufacturing of Carbon/Carbon composite requires long processing times and yields significant part rejection ratios. A critical stage of the material process is First Carbonization, in which the cured carbon/phenolic part is subjected to a pyrolysis treatment in order to remove all organic volatiles and leave behind a solid carbon residue. Current processing sensors are typically restricted to thermocouples, which provide feedback for control of the time/temperature schedule of the process. This paper describes recent results obtained with an in-situ technique[1-3] based on Acoustic Emission(AE) for the detection of the onset and development of macroporosity. Particular emphasis is placed on the possible observation of an effect similar to the Kaiser Effect.

II. CARBONIZATION PROCESS

When carbon phenolic, constructed of carbon fibers embedded in a phenolformaldehyde resin matrix, is subjected to pyrolysis thermochemical decomposition occurs. During this process the virgin polymer chain is broken down under a series of largely endothermic reactions and decomposed into water vapor, pyrolysis gases and a solid carbon residue. Stoichiometry of the pyrolysis gases reveals carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, hydrogen, nitrogen, methane and lesser products.

A number of researchers have developed numerical methods to predict the thermal response of polymeric materials during thermochemical decomposition. Kung[4] developed a numerical procedure based upon conservation of energy that was capable of predicting through-the-thickness temperature profiles. Equations for solid mass loss and the creation of gas mass were derived from the first-order Arrhenius reaction equation. Kansa et al[5] expanded Kung's approach by adding a storage term to the gas mass conservation equation and by defining the gas diffusion in terms of the Darcey flow law. This allowed them to model the accumulation and subsequent diffusion of the pyrolysis gases through the porous, decomposing solid. Henderson and Wiecek[6] have included an expansion/contraction model into a numerical solution scheme, which is similar in nature to Kansa et al., but directed towards the analysis of decomposing polymeric composites. The result is an analytical tool which models a thermally degrading polymer and accounts for the thermal expansion of the solid matrix, the decomposition of solid mass and accompanying solid contraction, the creation of a gas mass and its subsequent diffusion and coupled convection and conduction heat transfer.

Recently, Sullivan and Salamon[7] have developed a finite element formulation based upon the hypothesis that the thermomechanical response of polymeric composites is directly related to the diffusion of and porepressures created by gaseous byproducts generated during chemical decomposition. They calculated average longitudinal stress and lateral strain as a function of temperature for several values of the poroelastic parameters. They show a systematic rise with a peak at about 500°C, followed by a sudden dramatic drop at 550-600°C in good agreement with experimental data obtained at high heating rates (~6°C/s). Figure 1 shows an example of their results for longitudinal strain. Here the plane of the carbon fabric is assumed perpendicular to the longitudinal axis of the specimen, along which the strain is calculated and measured.

Fig. 1. Average longitudinal strain results from three plane stress solutions with three different values of the poroelastic parameters. (Courtesy Sullivan and Salamon [7])

III. EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

The approach was tailored to laboratory experiments in order to show feasibility. Therefore, the samples, the acoustics, the AE analysis and heating procedures were chosen with simplicity in mind and do not represent simulations of the manufacturing environment.

III.1. Sample Description

The material used in these experiments was 2-D woven, laminar composite, which was in a state just prior carbonization; i.e. after the curing process. In this state the samples were typically hard, brittle and dense, with some cross-linking and a few cracks and voids. The open pore porosity was less than 1% and the density about 1.4 gm/cm^3 . The geometry of the samples were in the form of rectangular plates with thicknesses ranging from 3.5 mm to 8.0 mm. The weave was 7 over, one under with the fibers nominally 10 microns in diameter and the lamina about 150 - 200 micron thick. As the samples were heated to 750°C they pyrolyzed with the liberation of organic volatiles. After the heat treatment, the samples had shrunk in thickness by about 7%, lost about 14% of their weight and had a much higher volume fraction of cracks and voids. The open pore porosity now was about 20% and the density about 1.3 gm/cm^3 . The elastic constants were measured before and after pyrolysis and the plates appear to be nearly transversely isotropic with respect to the plate normal. The Rayleigh wave speeds decreased as a result of pyrolysis from $0.9365V_s$ to $0.9052V_s$, respectively, where V_s is the shear wave velocity. The ultrasonic attenuation was also measured before and after in the range from 0.5 MHz to 10 MHz and was found to increase dramatically above about 2.5 MHz.

III.2. Acoustic Waveguides

The experimental apparatus used in the measurements consisted of a furnace with access ports on each end. Since the carbonization process involves the heating of the component up to 750°C , the acoustic sensors had to be attached to the part via waveguides. These were 3.2 mm thick and fashioned from high temperature alloy. Both stainless steel and Inconel 718 were found to work well. On one end the waveguides were attached to the sample near the edges[1,2]. In contrast to simply resting the waveguide against the sample, a gain of 10-15 dB in signal-to-noise ratio could be achieved by drilling and tapping the composite plate and then threading the matching end of the waveguide into the sample. This connection was bonded adhesively using a drop resin, which was allowed to polymerize at approximately 160°C prior to each run. The other end of the waveguide was attached to a horn terminating in a small platform onto which standard acoustic emission detectors were lightly clamped with high viscosity silicone oil as couplant. A typical manufacturing floor setting does not preclude this type of attachment of the waveguide, because the final shaping of the parts typically involves removal of some material from the part edges.

III.3. Instrumentation

The Acoustic Emission(AE) signals were captured, stored and analyzed with the help of Physical Acoustics Corporation Locan-AT 4-channel Analyzer. The AE activity was parametrized on a statistical basis by counting threshold crossings at each of several amplitudes which are evenly spaced on a log scale. The threshold amplitudes selected were 31.6 microvolts, 178 microvolts, 1 millivolt and 5.62 millivolts, all referenced to the transducer output. The most sensitive setting was approximately 7 dB above background electronic noise. The use of multiple thresholds allowed the discrimination between low amplitude events, which comprise the majority of AE activity and are thought to be associated with microcracking and the few large amplitude events observed to be associated with delaminations.

III.4. Heating Schedule

The heating rates were typically chosen to be constant for a given run and varied between 5°C/hr and 75°C/Hr . However, as shown later, there were several cases for which the heating rate was varied throughout the run in order to reveal some interesting effect.

IV ACOUSTIC EMISSION RESULTS

IV.1. AE Data During Heat-up and Cool-down

Figure 2 shows an example of AE data obtained during heat-up and cool-down. In Fig 2a. is shown the temperature as a function of time as measured with the aid of a thermocouple suspended just above the sample. In Fig. 2b. is shown the cumulative AE counts as measured by acoustic signals crossing the 178microvolt threshold. The major contribution to accumulation of counts occurs during pyrolysis but not until 400°C when matrix shrinkage is known to be the dominant factor. Little or no AE is observed while the furnace is on hold at about 700°C. Additional activity appears during cool-down, presumably as a consequence of differential thermal expansion of the constituents, i.e., fibers and solid carbon, and of the closing of the microcracks created during decomposition.

Figure 2. AE measurements during representative heating/cooling cycle during first carbonization of carbon/phenolic composite. Fig. 2a. Part temperature. Fig. 2b Cumulative AE counts above 178 microvolt threshold.

IV.2. AE Data during Pyrolysis

The focus of most of the measurements was the AE activity in the heat-up region. Figure 3 shows AE counts in the temperature range from room temperature to about 750°C. It is evident that aside from some counts around 100°C, the majority of AE is in the range from 450°C to about 750°C

with a peak at about 550°C. These data were obtained with the 30 dB threshold and with a constant temperature rate of increase at 75°C/Hr.

In order to test the repeatability of the AE measurements, three separate experiments were conducted on three specimens (SPAM, SPAL and SPAK) prepared from the same parent sample. Figure 3 shows the superposition of the measured AE counts averaged over 3 minute intervals and not cumulated over the run. The heat-up rate was identical. Aside from some fine structure, the repeatability is good. The fine structure is a result of interrupting the heat-up in order to remove some small coupons for microstructural analysis.

It is too early to identify the peak of AE activity with the rapid changes and reversals in the average longitudinal strain as calculated by Sullivan and Salamon[7]. But it is clear that the peak of AE activity very likely corresponds to the poroelastic regime, in which decomposition occurs and pore pressures are high, both leading to severe microcracking.

Fig. 3 Superposition of three 75°C/Hr runs with AE threshold crossing counts versus temperature.

IV.3. Kaiser Effect

The Kaiser Effect is well known to occur during the reapplication of a load after a prior loading. The AE all but stops until the load increases beyond that previously reached. A similar phenomenon was observed in pyrolysis here. As shown in Fig. 4 when a temperature of 492°C was achieved the temperature was reduced to 477°C over about an hour. The AE counts

diminished by a factor of about 2. Then when the temperature was increased again the AE seized almost completely and did not start again until the temperature was increased well beyond its old value, finally reaching its old value at about 505°C.

Fig. 4 Decrease in acoustic signals caused by successive cooling and heating of partially carbonized composite

V. DISCUSSION

The data suggest three stages of AE activity correlated with corresponding stages of microcracking. The results are consistent with the interpretation in terms of a competition between two main physical changes which are concomitant with the chemical changes. The two sources of stress are the shrinkage of the matrix and the thermal expansion of the matrix and fiber material.

The cracks within the "as cured" material can be explained by the difference in thermal expansion between the fibers, which actually have a negative coefficient of thermal expansion along their length, and the matrix material. Although the plate is able to shrink homogeneously during cooling in the direction perpendicular to the laminations, the fibers prevent this from occurring in the plane of the laminations. Therefore, at temperatures below the cure temperature the fiber bundles support a compressive load along their length, and the resulting tensile load in the matrix in the plane orthogonal to the plane of the lamination and parallel to the fiber direction causes the cracks observed.

As the sample is heated these cracks start to close, and should be closed completely as the sample once again reaches the curing temperature, at approximately 160°C. At higher temperatures the fiber bundles go into tension along their length and the matrix goes into compression in the plane orthogonal to the plane of the lamination and parallel to the fiber direction. Since the fibers can support these tensile loads, as long as the matrix remains in compression, the observed lack of cracking and associated AE is a consequence.

In stage 2 (450°C - 650°C) the phenolic resin breaks down chemically. This stage may be equivalent to the poroelastic stage proposed by Sullivan and Salamon[7]. Gases evolve and are released from the specimen through the pre-existing crack structure. Even though the resin is shrinking volumetrically at this point, it is still not in tension because of the residual thermally induced compressive stresses. In fact, the carbonization and associated matrix shrinkage must progress to a degree before the stresses in the matrix once again become tensile in the direction orthogonal to the fiber axes. At this point, inferred by AE to be between 450° and 500°C, severe microcracking starts to occur. This continues with increasing temperature until carbonization has been completed. Finally in stage 3, the effects of thermal expansion again dominate causing the matrix to be in compression. In this regime gas analysis measurements show a substantial evolution in H₂ gas. It is conjectured that there may be a phase transformation giving rise to some additional shrinkage and the AE activity shows some microcracking. The scenario described above is thought to hold for "normal" runs in which the heating rate is low and no significant damage such as delaminations are produced.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper describes an advanced sensor technique for monitoring the pyrolysis of Carbon/Phenolic in the material processing of carbon/carbon. The technique is based on the *in-situ* observation of acoustic emissions resulting from the onset and development of macroporosity associated with the decomposition of the phenolic. Although the technique's feasibility is demonstrated in a laboratory setting, application appears to be conducive to the manufacturing floor. In particular, the use of a long slender rod as acoustic waveguide to provide an acoustic path between the hot component in the furnace and the cold transducer outside the furnace, would appear to require only a slight modification to most carbonization systems. The attachment of the waveguide to the edge of the part, which ultimately is machined away, does not appear to present a problem. The paper further shows and demonstrates the repeatability of the measurements focussing on the poroelastic regime during heat-up. It also points to an interesting phenomenon that happens when the temperature is reduced and increased again. Similarly to what is observe in the Kaiser effect during re-application of a load the AE activity seized almost completely until the same of higher temperature is applied again. Finally the observations are linked to recent advances in the understanding of the carbonization process, as developed by calculations and interpretation of supporting data not presented here, such as SEM microscopy, weight loss, permeability, mass spectroscopy and shrinkage data.

Acknowledgements

The authors gratefully acknowledge the partial support of SAIC through the Air Force Materials Laboratory under Contract F33615-90-C-590, the Rockwell International Science Center through the Office of Naval Research under Contract N00014-87-C-0724 and funds from the Penn State university Bayard Kunkle Professorship.

References

1. Bulau, J.R., "AE Monitoring for Control of Carbon-Carbon Pyrolysis", Proceedings of IEEE 1988 Ultrasonics Symposium (B. R. McAvoy, Editor), IEEE Cat. No 88 CH 2578-3, 1988, pp. 1057-1063.
2. Tittmann, B.R., and Bulau, J.R., "Acoustic Emission and Ultrasonic Sensing for Carbon-Carbon Pyrolysis Monitoring" in Intelligent Processing of Materials, Haydn N. G. Wadley and W. Eugene Eckhart, Jr., eds (The Minerals, Metal and Material Society), 2, 1990, pp. 267-274.
3. Tittmann, B.R., "Acoustic Emission Sensors for NDC of Carbon/Carbon" In Nondestructive Characterization of Materials IV, Edited by C. O Ruud et al., Plenum Press, New York, 1992, pp. 167-172.
4. Kung, H.C., Combustion Flame, Vol. 18, 1972, pp. 185-195
5. Kansa, E.J., Perlee, H.E., and Chaiken, R.F., Combustion Flame, Vol. 29, 1977, pp. 311-324.
6. Henderson, J.B., and Wiecek, T. E., Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 21, 1987, pp. 373-393.
7. Sullivan, R.M. and Salamon, N.J., "A Finite Element Method for the Thermochemical Decomposition of Polymeric Materials-II. Carbon Phenolic Composites", International Journal of Engineering Science, Vol. 30, No. 7, 1992, pp. 939-951.